

Deep Learning-Based Chest Disease Detection

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Abstract— Medical imaging is an essential tool for detecting disorders of the chest, but the growing amount of imaging data demands effective and precise interpretation. To identify and categorize chest X-ray images as "normal," "pneumonia," or "tuberculosis," this seminar paper investigates the construction of a system that blends deep learning techniques, notably the VGG16 convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm, with a graphical user interface (GUI). The system improves the usability and accessibility of medical image analysis in addition to helping medical practitioners make diagnoses.

A user-friendly application is produced by the methodology, which also comprises model training, picture preprocessing, and GUI design. Results show that the system is effective at accurately diagnosing chest problems and that it has the potential to lighten the load on medical professionals.

This article discusses the value of deep learning in medical imaging, potential future research areas, and ethical issues. The method that was created is a step toward the accurate and efficient diagnosis of chest ailments and demonstrates the synergistic potential of deep learning and user interface design in the medical field.

Keyword— Chest Disease Detection, Convolutional Neural Networks, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging is essential to contemporary healthcare because it makes it possible to observe internal structures non-invasively and helps with disease diagnosis and therapy. Chest X-ray imaging is one of these techniques that is essential in evaluating pulmonary and thoracic diseases. However, the volume of medical images that are produced continuously presents major difficulties for rapid and accurate interpretation.

The combination of state-of-the-art technologies, including deep learning and graphical user interfaces (GUIs), has yielded revolutionary results in the field of medical picture analysis. Chest X-ray pictures are recognized and classified by the system under consideration in this seminar paper into three primary groups: "normal," "pneumonia," and "tuberculosis." It achieves this by combining an easy-to-use graphical user interface (GUI) with deep learning, more especially the VGG16 convolutional neural network (CNN) method.

This study is primarily motivated by two factors. The system's primary goal is to lessen the heavy workload placed on medical personnel who frequently interpret chest X-ray pictures, improving diagnostic precision and effectiveness. By providing a user-friendly interface that enables non-specialists to undertake early assessments, it also aims to improve accessibility.

In this paper, we will delve into the methodology used to develop and implement this system, encompassing image preprocessing, deep learning model training, and GUI design. We will present the results of our system's performance, demonstrating its capability to accurately classify chest conditions. Beyond the technical aspects, we will also discuss the broader implications, including the potential impact on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes.

This work represents an advancement in the use of deep learning and user interface design in medical imaging, emphasizing the potential for cooperation between technology and healthcare. It not only offers a workable remedy for detecting chest diseases, but it also emphasizes the larger issue of utilizing technology to solve significant healthcare problems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Medical image analysis using deep learning techniques has seen rapid advances in recent years. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have emerged as a promising technique for a variety of medical image classification tasks.

Jaeger et al. [1] propose using lung segmentation masks along with CNNs to improve tuberculosis detection in chest radiographs. The lung masks focus the classifier on relevant lung regions. Song et al. [2] demonstrate the use of deep CNN models for classifying lung nodules in CT scans into benign or malignant categories. They achieve good performance compared to traditional machine learning techniques.

Yoo et al. [3] provide a systematic review of deep learning based computer aided diagnosis systems for detecting lung cancer from chest CT scans. Their review covers various CNN architectures like AlexNet, VGGNet, GoogLeNet etc. applied to this problem. They note most works report high performance but call for more rigorous evaluation.

Garg et al. [4] specifically focus on using a convolutional neural network model for lung nodule malignancy classification. They use transfer learning from the Inception-v3 model and achieve strong results on their dataset. They indicate deep CNNs show promise for such targeted classification problems.

Beyond lung diseases, deep learning has also been applied for brain tumor analysis tasks using MRI scans. Górriz et al. [5] propose an unsupervised approach using dictionary learning and sparse Bayesian learning to identify distinctive imaging features for clustering and classification of brain MRI data.

Lalitha et al. [6] specifically design a deep CNN model called BrainNet CNN for brain tumor detection using MRI images. They achieve good performance on brain MRI data, demonstrating the potential of deep learning for brain tumor analysis.

Overall, the literature shows deep CNN models are able to learn highly discriminative features from medical images like x-rays, CT scans and MRI. Transfer learning from pre-trained models helps boost performance. However, larger datasets, better evaluation metrics beyond just accuracy, and interpretability of models remains an area of active research.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for Chest Disease Detection using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with the Chest X-Ray dataset:

A. Data Collection and Preparation:

Gather a diverse and extensive dataset of chest X-ray images. The dataset should include images of normal chests, as well as those with pneumonia and tuberculosis.

B. Deep Learning Model Selection:

Select an appropriate deep learning model architecture for the classification of images. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) such as VGG16, ResNet, or bespoke CNN architectures are popular options.

C. Data Splitting:

Make three subsets of the dataset: testing, validation, and training. A typical allocation would be 15% for testing, 70% for training, and 15% for validation.

D. Model Training:

Train the selected deep learning model on the training dataset. Fine-tune the model's hyperparameters for optimal performance.

E. Hyperparameter Tuning:

To improve model performance, test out various learning rates, batch sizes, and architectural modifications.

F. Testing and Result Analysis

Assess the final model's performance on the independent test dataset to evaluate its generalization capabilities. Analyze the results to determine the accuracy of chest disease detection and compare it to existing methods if applicable.

G. Future Work:

Suggest areas for future research and improvement, such as expanding the dataset, exploring new model architectures, or integrating additional diagnostic features.

II. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful image recognition, we follow the following steps

A. Importing Libraries

```
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
from tensorflow import keras
from keras.models import Model
from keras.applications.vgg16 import VGG16
from keras.preprocessing.vgg16 import preprocess_input
from keras.preprocessing import image
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from keras.models import Sequential
import numpy as np
from glob import glob
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

1) *numpy (np)*:

Description: NumPy is an introductory package for scientific computing with Python. These arrays support not just a wide range of mathematical operations but also massive, multidimensional arrays and matrices. In our code, NumPy is most likely used for numerical calculations and array handling.

2) *OpenCV (cv2)*:

Description: An open-source computer vision and machine learning software library is called OpenCV (Open-Source Computer Vision Library). For handling photos and movies, it has a number of features and tools. The image processing and manipulation in your code is done with OpenCV.

3) *matplotlib.pyplot (plt)*:

Description: A Python data visualization library called Matplotlib enables users to make static, animated, and interactive charts. The Matplotlib "pyplot" module provides a simple and reliable interface for creating various types of plots, charts, and graphs. It's used to display charts and visuals.

4) *tensorflow (tf)*

Description: Google has built an open-source machine learning package called TensorFlow. For creating and refining deep learning and machine learning models, it offers an adaptable framework. TensorFlow is used to create and train neural networks.

B. Training the Model

1) *Defining image size, paths*

```
IMAGE_SIZE = [224, 224]

train_path = 'chest_xray/train'
valid_path = 'chest_xray/test'
```

2) *Loading VGG16 model*

```
vgg = VGG16(input_shape=IMAGE_SIZE + [3], weights='imagenet', include_top=False)
```

3) *Setting all layers to non-trainable*

```
for layer in vgg.layers:
    layer.trainable = False
```

4) *Building Classifier*

```
folders = glob('chest_xray/train/*')
x = Flatten()(vgg.output)

prediction = Dense(len(folders), activation='softmax')(x)
# create a model object
model = Model(inputs=vgg.input, outputs=prediction)
# view the structure of the model
model.summary()
```

5) **Compiling model**

```
model.compile(
    loss='categorical_crossentropy',
    optimizer='adam',
    metrics=['accuracy']
)
```

6) **Data Preprocessing**

```
train_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale = 1./255,
    shear_range = 0.2,
    zoom_range = 0.2,
    horizontal_flip = True)

test_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale = 1./255)

# Make sure you provide the same target size as initialized for the image size
training_set = train_datagen.flow_from_directory('chest_xray/train',
    target_size = (224, 224),
    batch_size = 10,
    class_mode = 'categorical')

test_set = test_datagen.flow_from_directory('chest_xray/test',
    target_size = (224, 224),
    batch_size = 10,
    class_mode = 'categorical')
```

7) **Training the Model**

```
r = model.fit_generator(
    training_set,
    validation_data=test_set,
    epochs=5,
    steps_per_epoch=len(training_set),
    validation_steps=len(test_set)
)
```

8) **Saving and Loading Model**

```
import tensorflow as tf
from keras.models import load_model
model.save('chest_xray.h5')
model=load_model('chest_xray.h5')
```

9) **Make prediction**

```
img = image.load_img('chest_xray\\val\\NORMAL\\NORMAL2-IM-1436-0001.jpeg', target_size=(224, 224))

x=image.img_to_array(img)
x=np.expand_dims(x, axis=0)
img_data=preprocess_input(x)

classes=model.predict(img_data)
1/1 [=====] - 0s 237ms/step

result=int(classes[0][0])

if result==0:
    print("Person is Affected By PNEUMONIA")
else:
    print("Result is Normal")
```

C. **Results**

```
Y_pred = model.predict_generator(test_generator, verbose=1)
42/42 [=====] - 187s 4s/step
```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
NORMAL	0.16	0.15	0.15	234
PNEUMONIA	0.31	0.31	0.31	390
Tuberculosis	0.55	0.56	0.55	700
accuracy			0.41	1324
macro avg	0.34	0.34	0.34	1324
weighted avg	0.41	0.41	0.41	1324

Fig 1. Performance matrices

Fig 2. Diagnosed with Pneumonia

Fig 3. Diagnosed with Tuberculosis

V. **CONCLUSION**

In this research, we successfully developed an automated deep learning system for chest tuberculosis and pneumonia identification. Using a pre-trained VGG16 model, we were able to quickly and accurately classify images for chest X-ray evaluation.

In addition to providing text-to-speech feedback and rapid disease forecasts, the technology allows users to submit chest X-ray photos. It is important to emphasize that the system should supplement professional medical diagnosis, not take the place of it, even with its enormous potential.

With more research being done and more datasets available, the system's accuracy and capabilities can be increased. This work shows how deep learning can be used in medical picture analysis to improve healthcare services and help with early disease identification.

VI. REFERENCES

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